

Wide hybridization between rice and most of its wild relatives is now possible. Genes for insect resistance from *O.*

officinalis have been successfully incorporated into advanced breeding lines. Therefore, the various sources of

resistance reported are potential donors for resistance to the tungro viruses. □

Performance of a bacterial blight (BB)-resistant rice variety in the endemic pockets of Konkan Region, India

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Karjat 1 (Holamaldiga/IR36) is an early-maturing rice with high resistance to BB at both the vegetative phase and flower-

ing stage. The variety, released by KKV, is specifically for the BB-endemic areas of Konkan Region (west coast).

The variety and susceptible checks EK70 (local) and Karjat 184 were tested during the five kharif (monsoon) seasons of 1985-86 to 1989-90, in farmers' fields. We recorded BB incidence three times using the *Standard evaluation system for rice (SES)* 0-9 scale.

At vegetative phase, Karjat 1 was free of BB as foliar and kreshek infec-

tions during all years studied (see table). Average incidence of BB at flowering and grain filling ranged from 0.12 to 1.24, with a maximum of 0.4 at flowering stage and 1.5 at grain filling. Average incidence of BB was 3.90-6.72 on Karjat 184 and 3.92-7.22 on EK70.

Karjat 184 had an average kreshek infection of 3.54 and EK70, 3.64.

The study indicates that farmers can adopt Karjat 1 for cultivation in BB-endemic areas of Konkan Region. □

Performance of Karjat 1, Karjat 184, and EK70 in BB endemic areas in Konkan Region, India, 1985-86 to 1989-90.

Year	Locations (no.)	Av BB incidence ^a												
		Vegetative ^b				BB at flowering			BB at grain filling			Av grain yield (t/ha)		
		Karjat 184		EK70		Karjat I	Karjat 184	EK70	Karjat I	Karjat 184	EK70	Karjat I	Karjat 184	EK70
		BB	Kreshek	BB	Kreshek									
1985-86	5	0.0	0.1	1.4	2.4	0.4	2.4	6.2	1.0	4.6	7.2	4.2	3.9	2.8
1986-87	5	7.7	7.0	5.0	4.4	0.1	6.2	5.2	1.2	6.5	5.4	3.6	1.6	2.6
1987-88	4	5.0	2.4	5.0	3.0	0.1	7.2	7.0	1.5	9.0	8.0	4.1	2.8	2.8
1988-89	2	2.4	2.0	3.2	2.4	0.0	4.6	4.9	1.0	6.2	6.5	3.7	3.0	2.9
1989-90	6	4.4	6.2	5.0	6.0	0.0	5.6	5.6	1.5	7.3	9.0	3.2	2.0	1.8
Av		3.00	3.54	3.92	3.64	0.12	5.16	5.78	1.24	6.72	7.22	3.8	2.7	2.6

^a 1976 SES scale for BB: 0 = no BB incidence. 9 = 5 100% area of upper 3 leaves showing necrotic symptoms. SES scale for kreshek: 0 = no incidence. 9 = 91-100% hills affected. ^b Karjat 1 had no BB at vegetative phase.

Pest resistance—insects

Insecticide-induced resurgence of brown planthopper (BPH) on IR62

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Many farmers in Koronadal, Philippines, apply sprays of synthetic pyrethroids to their rice as early as 1-2 wk after transplanting (WT) regardless of numbers of insect pests or beneficial arthropods. These sprays are perceived as "insur-

ance"—even when varieties have insect resistance. Resurgence of BPH populations on susceptible varieties due to the destruction of natural enemies is well documented. Little information is available, however, on the impact of these chemical sprays on BPH and natural enemy populations on resistant rice varieties.

We established a trial in a farmer's field in Caloocan, Koronadal, during the 1986 wet season (Jul-Sep) to demonstrate the effects of broad-spectrum chemical applications on BPH and spiders (major BPH predators) on resistant variety IR62. An area of 800 m² was planted and divided into two equal parts. One part was sprayed at 10 days after transplanting (DT) with a synthetic pyrethroid

BPH and spiders (no./20 hills)

Total number of BPH and spiders sampled by D-vac. Caloocan, South Cotabato, Philippines, 1986 wet season.